

COMMENTARY ON FIRST AID EDUCATION CURRICULUM

Dilafuz Sulaymonova

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

awesome-ds@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12155530>

Introduction to the poster and curriculum

The proposed First Aid Education Curriculum in the poster is intended for rural pupils aged 12 to 15 in Uzbekistan and would be sponsored by the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan and the Red Crescent Society of Uzbekistan. Emergency medical care for accidents and sudden illnesses has advanced significantly in recent years. However, even the most well-organized medical treatment can be ineffective and delayed if the injured person is not provided with the necessary first aid in time. Growing up in today's complex world, children and youth need to understand how to stay safe and healthy, as well as how to manage their academic, personal, and social lives in a positive manner (DfE, 2021). Therefore, providing secondary school pupils with the basic life skills is the core objective of this curriculum and gives an opportunity for pupils at KS 3-4 levels for reasonable responding to emergency cases.

Content of the curriculum

As it is highlighted in several findings, the critical importance of providing first aid lessons in schools is to address the public's lack of knowledge and confidence in responding to a first aid emergency (British Red Cross, 2018). Moreover, the school provides an atmosphere in which a large number of individuals can be trained at a reasonable cost (Toner et al., 2007; Fleischhackl et al., 2009; Banfai et al., 2017). Another important factor is school pupils are more likely to be involved in accidents and injuries because of physical activity at school and in their neighbourhoods. These activities include participation in school events such as sports, as well as simply playing, riding, and swimming (Mohd Sharif et al., 2018). The UK Government has recognized the importance of first aid and approved it as a mandatory element of the PSHE curriculum in schools. Learning these life save skills is an important chance for youngsters transitioning to secondary school to reinforce safety lessons (DfE, 2014).

Following these and considering local and international crises occurring currently across the globe, the curriculum is recommended for pupils living in the countryside to provide them with the basic knowledge and skills they need to care for themselves and obtain assistance if difficulties emerge.

Children do not learn in the same manner that adults do; therefore, training materials should be properly made and updated to be easily accessible to young people in order to foster meaningful learning and improve not just students' understanding but also information retention over time (Connolly et al., 2007). First aid education cannot cover all the broad topics of first aid because it must be accessible to school- aged children quickly and easily. Teachers with special certificates in the school buildings carry out this additional education, special representatives from emergency centers are also involved in practical training, and children visit community centers to feel the real situation and practice all obtained knowledge with specific essentials such as medical manikins and AED equipment.

In attracting children to this course, attention is paid to the following skills:

- communication skills;
- an aptitude for absorbing new information;
- the ability to cope with physically hard and unpleasant emergency procedures;
- the availability to respond swiftly to an emergency;
- the ability to maintain self-control when confronted with persons suffering from various emergency cases (bloody) (DfE, 2022).

Background to the curriculum

Curriculum refers to the set of subjects taught at school and the process of implementation of the main objectives and outcomes expected from them. According to Stabback (2016), in other words, curriculum serves as a link between education and development, and the competencies connected with lifelong learning and aligned with development needs in the broadest, most comprehensive sense span that link. More broadly, the curriculum is regarded as a political and social consensus that reflects a society's common vision while taking into consideration local, national, and global needs and expectations. When presenting a certain curriculum to the educational system and preparing its design, the changes in the world, the updates in this society, and the needs of the people living in it are carefully observed, and each of them is reflected in this curriculum so that it can also bring success to this country in the future. Considering the above factors, the presented curriculum is currently included in the public education system as an additional curriculum that children would undertake as an after-school club, but soon it will gain its importance like other subjects including school timetables. It is a one-month project mainly in the school area, includes 3 sessions per week, and students visit emergency and

community centers for practical training.

Purpose, aim, objectives, outcomes of the curriculum

As each curriculum is presented, its objectives and expected outcomes are determined while working on it. The objectives state what we want the students to learn in terms of knowledge, concepts, abilities, and attitudes. More tangibly, 'learning outcomes' may also be used to state what the children will be 'able to do' as a result of the teaching and learning programme, says Pollard (2014). The primary purpose of the proposed school-based first-aid curriculum is to teach students fundamental first-aid skills and information so that they can respond correctly in emergency circumstances, potentially saving lives and lowering the severity of injuries. The curriculum aims to teach students how to recognise emergencies, call for help, and perform urgent first aid until professional medical assistance comes with the help of weekly short-term curriculum activities. Furthermore, the curriculum could be designed to encourage safety awareness and injury prevention. By the end of the course, pupils will be able to know:

- basic first-aid for common medical injuries;
- life-saving abilities, such as CPR administration;
- the function of defibrillators and when they may be required (DfE, 2019).

General outcome of the curriculum is helping to overall community health and safety by teaching pupils basic first aid skills.

Conclusion

Rural public-school pupils will become competent first-aiders and AED users because of this focused, shortened training curriculum. This will be one of the state initiatives to examine secondary school students' capacity to acquire and maintain CPR and AED skills for victims of sudden cardiac arrest and unexpected accidents using such a programme. It is highly recommended and believed that PSHE is for schools to tailor their local PSHE programme to reflect the needs of their students; schools are expected to use their PSHE education programme to equip pupils with a solid understanding of risk and the knowledge and skills necessary to make safe and informed decisions. (DfE, September 13, 2021). When presenting the proposed curriculum, reference was made to the regulatory documents of Gov.Uk and the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Banfai B., Pek E., Pandur A., Csonka H., Betlehem J. (2017). 'The year of first aid': Effectiveness of a 3-day first aid programme for 7-14-year-old primary

- school children. *Emerg. Med. J.* 34:526–532. doi: 10.1136/emered-2016-206284.
2. Dfe (2014) National Curriculum in England: framework for key stages 3 and 4 framework document.
 3. London: HMSO
 4. Dfe (2019) Relationships Education, Relationships and Sex Education (RSE) and Health Education. Statutory guidance for governing bodies, proprietors, head teachers, principals, senior leadership teams, teachers
 5. Dfe (2021) Personal, social, health and economic (PSHE) education.
 6. Fleischhackl R., Nuernberger A., Sterz F., Schoenberg C., Urso T., Habart T., Mittlboeck M., Chandra-Strobos N. (2009). Schoolchildren sufficiently apply life supporting first aid: A prospective investigation. *Crit. Care.* 2009; 13:R127. doi: 10.1186/cc7984
 7. Nur Amirah Mohd Sharif, Muhammad Kamil Che Hasan, Farrah Ilyani Che Jamaludin, Mohd Khairul Zul Hasymi Firdaus. (2018). The need for first aid education for adolescents. *Enfermería Clínica.* Volume 28, Supplement 1, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1130-8621\(18\)30028-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1130-8621(18)30028-7)
 8. Philip Stabback. (2016). What makes a Quality Curriculum? March, No 2. IBE/2016/WP/CD/02
 9. Pollard, Andrew, et al. (2014). *Reflective Teaching in Schools*, Bloomsbury Publishing, ProQuest Ebook Central, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/bham/detail.action?docID=1630373>.
 10. Toner P., Connolly M., Laverty L., McGrath P., Connolly D., McCluskey D.R. (2007). Teaching basic life support to school children using medical students and teachers in a 'peer-training' model— Results of the 'ABC for life' programme. *Resuscitation.* 007;75:169–175. doi: 10.1016/j.resuscitation.2007.03.009.
 11. Tse, E., Plakitsi, K., Voulgaris, S., & Alexiou, G. A. (2023). The Role of a First Aid Training Program for Young Children: A Systematic Review. *Children*,10(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10030431>

